

Target Reacquisition and Identification Using Real-Time Visual Odometry and 3D Reconstruction of Underwater Scenes

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Abstract

An increasing number of navies are considering how to exploit unmanned systems for Mine Counter-Measures (MCM) missions in order to remove the man from the minefield. In a mine hunting scenario involving unmanned surface and underwater vehicles, several targets have been localized thanks to a first vehicle equipped with long range high frequency sonar. Because of a target's positional uncertainty produced between the first system and the vehicle dedicated to the identification, a step of target reacquisition needs to be performed in order to identify it. This step remains challenging and tedious because it implies to survey an underwater area of over hundred square meters with restricted camera views, poor visibility and sometimes high clutter density, increasing the risk that the vehicle never finds or incorrectly acquires its target.

This paper describes the use of underwater photogrammetry as a potential solution for target reacquisition and identification with unmanned underwater vehicles. The 3D modeling system creates photorealistic and high resolution three-dimensional model of a seafloor area. While the real time estimation of the cameras motion, which is performed during the 3D reconstruction, is addressed as a navigation aid during the photogrammetric survey. Initial results of underwater surveys and 3D modeling are presented.

Keywords: Mine Counter-Measures, Target Reacquisition, Visual Odometry, Underwater Photogrammetry, 3D Reconstruction, Unmanned Underwater Vehicles.

1 Introduction

For several years, DGA Naval Systems, an organization belonging to the French Ministry of Defense, has been studying the use of unmanned systems to conduct mine hunting operations. The traditional method for conducting Mine Counter-Measures (MCM) missions, which includes steps like detection, classification, identification and neutralization, is through the use of manned ships and divers. By introducing the use of Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USV) and Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUV), we plan to reduce cost and time and to keep personnel away from risk. But the execution of the MCM phases with unmanned vehicles introduces new operational challenges. One of these

challenges is the target reacquisition task which needs to be achieved when considering a mine hunting scenario that starts with the deployment of a primary system dedicated to perform a large area survey with long range active sonar. This can be done by using an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) equipped with Synthetic Aperture Sonar (SAS) or an Unmanned Surface Vehicle (USV) equipped with towed fish SAS. The first goal is to generate a search-classify-map of mine-like objects (MLOs). The search-classify-map is then exploited by an operator through a post-mission analysis to select which contact to investigate, identify and eventually neutralize. At this time, MLOs position information is provided to a second system. This can be a Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) deployed from an USV or an AUV which goes out at a later time and uses a suite of short-range sensors to perform MLOs reacquisition and identification (RI).

In order to achieve its mission, the second system has to deal with the positional uncertainty between the two systems which produces localization errors from several meters to tens of meters. This implies to operate survey areas increased by as much as several hundred square meters. We note that the same target reacquisition issue appears in a mine hunting scenario that involves a third vehicle following the identification vehicle and dedicated to the mine's neutralization task.

To ensure the effectiveness of future targets reacquisition and identification missions, it is essential to ensure that once in the area, the underwater vehicle will be able to investigate all the uncertainty area of the contact with the assurance that its sensors will provide usable images of the contact and its surrounding neighborhood and with a short enough time of research in order to avoid abandonment of the mission.

Considering a ROV deployed from an USV, the pilot of the ROV will have to ensure to cover an entire search area of several hundred square meters without omitting any part likely to include the desired target. The problem is even more complex considering an AUV deployed to survey, in an autonomous way, an area of several hundred square meters, distant to several kilometers, with high clutter density. The vehicle must operate autonomous decision making capabilities that will permit the investigation of the entire area, in a most correct way possible, in order to return usable images of the target in post-mission analysis.

This paper presents the use of real-time visual odometry and 3D modeling techniques to perform accurately a survey for target's reacquisition and identification. In Section 2, before presenting the whole process of data acquisition and processing, we discuss the optimal execution of an underwater search mission and how real-time visual odometry can be used as navigation aid. Results of high resolution underwater 3D modeling are presented in Section 3 in order to show some identification capabilities.

2 Underwater Search Survey and Three-Dimensional Reconstruction

2.1 The problem of underwater search and recovery

As mentioned previously, with the introduction of unmanned systems in MCM operations, the true location of the target is lost between the detect-and-classify phase and the reacquire-and-identify phase. The reacquisition becomes similar to an underwater search-and-retrieve scenario in an unknown seafloor area of ten by ten meters.

Without prior knowledge of the scene, a reliable method is to constrain the vehicle to follow specific search patterns. For example (see Figure 1), one pattern can be the common parallel-track search pattern which provides uniform coverage when the estimated target's position is a rough approximation. The starting point of the pattern is initiated at a corner of the searching square

(a) Parallel-track search pattern

(b) Square-spiral search pattern

- Vehicle of reacquisition & identification
- Estimated position of the target
- True position of the target unknown from the vehicle
- Natural clutter

Figure 1: Illustration of the parallel track (a) and the square spiral (b) search patterns.

area in order to get the estimated position of the target in the middle of the square. Another is a square-spiral search pattern or expanding square search pattern. It consists of a square-shaped route that begins at a designated waypoint which is the estimated position of a target and continually expands away from the center. Search leg length is increased by one track space on every other leg.

Some rules need to be followed to achieve these particular patterns properly in order to get correct images for the processing. During the shooting, the images need to overlap no less than 75% of the image footprint overlap in order to perform 3D reconstruction thanks to matching correspondences between consecutive images. And there should also be at least 30% sidelap across-track. More than avoiding holes of coverage during the survey, the goal is to obtain back corresponding points from the previous parallel track line in order to reduce drift and keep consistency on the estimated vehicle trajectory.

By estimating the positions and orientations of a mobile, through the analysis of the image sequence from its camera (cameras), visual odometry (VO) appears to be an appropriate function to help the accurate accomplishment of the search patterns. During the trials, the ROV's pilot can access information on the vehicle's trajectory in order to follow the preplanned path and to correct eventual drift.

Considering an AUV sent at several nautical miles to conduct autonomously preplanned parallel-track or square-spiral patterns, the necessity to give the vehicle some ability to be aware of its current trajectory and to correct it if necessary is even stronger. In this case, the autonomous decision making of the vehicle shall deal with real-time visual odometry information in order to investigate the entire area, in a most correct way possible. Then, if the survey is done properly, there is a good chance to return usable images of the target and its surrounding neighborhood to post-mission analysis.

The algorithms which give the cameras positions and orientations and lead to the visual odometry functionality constitute initial steps of the three-dimensional reconstruction of a scene. These initial steps help to accomplish the survey dedicated to the target's reacquisition. After the reacquisition's survey, the acquired images can be stored and processed to perform the 3D modeling of the surveyed seafloor area potentially containing a mine. The 3D model offers then a significant visualization of the target and its surrounding neighborhood for identification purpose.

In the next section, the data acquisition and processing system which allows the real-time VO and 3D modelling will be presented. The described system is called ORUS 3D and is patented by COMEX and the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS).

2.2 Description of the data acquisition and processing system

2.2.1 Hardware and software architecture

The ORUS 3D system is a modular and distributed hardware and software architecture which is able to record a large quantity of data in a synchronous way while performing real-time computations. It is composed of an embedded system arranged in a removable assembly under a ROV and a computer located at the surface, which interacts with the ROV through an Ethernet TCP/IP link and permits in real-time the configuration and control of cameras and the computation and visualization of the visual odometry. The operator can pilot the ROV using a dedicated application that displays the position of the vehicle in real-time (see Figure 2) in order to ensure the complete coverage of the area to be surveyed.

Figure 2: Real-time visual odometry as seen from the on-board computer. This figure shows the 3D point cloud calculated over the surveyed zone and the position of the vehicle for each image pair. The density of the points measured on each image is colour-coded (yellow, green and black) which gives an overview of the quality of the orientation (yellow < 30 points, green between 100 and 200 points, dark green > 300 points).

The image acquisition module implements a trifocal system (see Figure 3 and 4) composed of one high-resolution, full-frame camera synchronized at 2 Hz and two low-resolution cameras synchronized at 10 Hz in order to perform efficient image footprint overlap needed by the photogrammetric process. The lighting system uses four spot LED flashlights synchronized with the acquisitions of the cameras, placed on the corners of a rectangle around the three cameras.

The trifocal synchronization mechanism is also used to tag images with homogeneous timestamps and to retrieve image pairs and image triples.

The data processing, described in detail later in this paper, takes place in different locations. First, the low resolution image pairs dedicated to visual odometry are processed on the embedded computer in real-time before they are stored with the high resolution images. The information extracted from the image pairs is then sent to the surface for calculation and visualization of the visual odometry. The 3D reconstruction of a high resolution metric model is finally performed offline with the contribution of the image triples.

Figure 3: Illustration of the ORUS 3D system “squid” composed of three camera housings, an embedded unit and a tilt to adjust camera orientation.

Figure 4: Photography of the three camera housings, the LED lighting flashes and the sonar altimeter for automatic exposure control.

2.2.2 Automatic control of the camera exposure

Operating underwater photogrammetric surveys implies navigating close to the seafloor. When following rough terrain such as rocks, scarps and slopes, the image acquisition system has to deal with ups and downs movements of the vehicle which cause variations in distance to the subject. These variations can be the cause of poor image quality, failure in real-time visual odometry and thus unsatisfactory final 3D reconstruction. Because the dynamic range of a photosensitive sensor is limited, it is not able to take well-exposed and equally bright images with the same lighting and camera settings for different illuminations of the scene. If the settings produce well-exposed close-up pictures, they will produce underexposed distant images. On the contrary, well-exposed distant images will cause overexposed and saturated close-up images. Another difficulty which impacts the image quality of the photogrammetric survey is the motion blur which occurs with the movement

of the vehicle.

To avoid these issues, it is necessary to automatically control the exposure and thus adapt the amount of light accepted by the camera. This can be done by adjusting automatically three camera settings: shutter speed, gain and aperture.

The shutter speed permits controlling the amount of time the shutter mechanism is open allowing light to enter the camera. It is related to the exposure time. To avoid overexposed images, a bright scene needs a fast shutter speed (short exposure time). On the other hand, to avoid underexposed images, a dark scene needs a long shutter speed (long exposure time). But the exposure time also directly influences the presence of motion blur in an image. If there are a lot of movements in the scene the exposure time needs to be short to avoid motion blur.

The gain, measured in decibels (dB), works as an electric charge that makes the sensor believe it is receiving more light than it actually does. Its value can be switched from 0 (no gain) to 18 dB or 32 dB or even more. The higher the gain, the lower the light level can be. The gain allows taking good images even with poor light conditions. However, the drawback of increased gain is an increase in noise causing the apparition of random speckles on the image.

The aperture setting refers to the opening of a lens's diaphragm through which light passes. A more open aperture allows more light and results in a lighter exposure. In the contrary, the exposure becomes darker with a smaller aperture. By affecting the way the lens focuses the rays of light, the aperture also controls the depth of field, which is the portion of a scene that appears to be sharp. If the aperture is very small, the depth of field is large, while if the aperture is large, the depth of field is small.

Because of their strong relationship, setting shutter speed, gain and aperture in order to have optimal exposure is not obvious. As soon as you set one parameter, you need to compromise with another.

All modern digital video cameras have built-in exposure control. The built-in exposure control automatically changes the exposure in order to get an average of mid-tone grey for the whole scene. This works well in most situations, but on a mobile platform with difficult lighting situations, the assumptions made by the built-in exposure control can produce non-optimal image exposure.

A way to obtain good image exposure could be to get in real time precise knowledge of the area of interest of the scene and the lighting condition and use it to control efficiently the exposure settings. The initial approach is the integration of a sonar altimeter next to the vision system for measuring in real-time the distance of the cameras from the seafloor all along the survey. This distance is given in real time by serial link to the camera controller to parameterize the exposure time. Initial experimental tests have permitted establishing and using a set of optimal exposure time values according to the system's lighting and distances from the seafloor.

2.2.3 Description of the image processing chain

Before initiating the data acquisition and processing chain, an initial procedure consists in the calibration of the trinocular system. The goal of calibration is to accurately measure the intrinsic parameters for each camera (interior orientation) and the extrinsic parameters (exterior orientation) in order to determine the relationship between the coordinate systems of the cameras. When the system is properly calibrated, the changing positions of the whole system in the 3D space can be performed and accurate and scaled measurements can be applied to the final 3D model.

The calibration is obtained in two phases. The first one is carried out on each camera's housing in order to compute intrinsic parameters depending on the water/glass interface of the housing. The approach described by Kwon et al. (2006), consisting in the use of standard photogrammetric calibration software, has been adopted. The second calibration phase is done to determine the

relative position of the three cameras which are securely mounted on a rigid platform. This can easily be done by taking multiple images of a calibration pattern before each mission.

Starting with the taking of multiple overlapped images, the photogrammetric processing chain is decomposed in two parts (see Figures 5 and 6). A part performed in real-time which consists of the visual odometry and a second part which consists of the post-processing of the information stored during the survey and leads to the final 3D reconstruction of the surveyed area.

Based on multiple view geometry fundamentals (Hartley and Zisserman, 2003), the first step of the real-time computation consists of calculating the relative motion between two consecutive stereo pairs of images. Using algorithms like SIFT (Lowe, 2004), SURF (Bay et al., 2006) or HARRIS detector (Gauglitz et al., 2011), the procedure starts with the detection and matching of feature points between the image quadruplet: previous left with current left, and previous right with current left. Using these matches, the corresponding fundamental matrices, which integrate the transformations between image pairs, are computed using RANSAC procedure as described in Hartley and Zisserman (2003). Based on the obtained fundamental matrices, the essential matrices, which embed the rotation and translation parameters, are then computed and decomposed to obtain camera rotation and translation parameters following Nistér (2004).

With the pose estimation for images quadruplets, the trajectory could be estimated by concatenating the cameras poses incrementally at each image pair-to-image pair motion but this initial pose estimation is marred by errors of re-projection and it generates over time a growing drift from the real path.

In order to handle this error accumulation, a traditional approach consists of performing a global optimization function, called bundle adjustment, which concatenates all the parameters for each camera pose and each 3D point of the global sequence to adjust the three dimensional positions of homologous points. But global bundle adjustment is time consuming and real-time processing is impossible for long sequences.

Trying to reach the best trade-off between real-time processing and accuracy, different approaches have been developed, referred to as sliding-window bundle adjustment or local bundle adjustment and based on the execution of the optimization function over a limited number of camera poses.

The method proposed by CNRS and COMEX, explained in the next section, is called semi-global visual odometry. It is also based on the use of a limited number of frames in the optimization process and its implementation is based on the speed-optimized BA toolbox proposed in Lourakis and Argyros (2009).

During the processing of the visual odometry and the orientation of all the images, a sparse 3D point cloud based on all the homologous points triangulated in 3D space is constructed. As soon as the images and the point cloud are transferred on board, a stage of densification is then performed with the contribution of the image triples to obtain the final 3D model. The procedure, based on the Patch-Based Multi View Stereo (PMVS) method (Furukawa and Ponce, 2010), uses the oriented images and the associated camera parameters to estimate the corresponding 3D point for almost every pixel in all images. This iterative technique exploits the epipolar geometry hypothesis to gather local image windows from several views and checks if they satisfy constraints like local photometric likelihood and viewpoint proximity in order to reconstruct small surfaces of 3D points (or patches) based on a cross correlation between gathered views. Then, iteratively, new 3D points are determined around those already found with the filtering procedure which removes erroneous patches that do not verify a global consistency.

Finally, for a more refined 3D model, at the cost of higher computation times, the dense point cloud can be connected to produce a continuous surface mesh over the model. The original images can be combined into a texture map applied to the surface of the model, resulting in a photorealistic

rendering.

Figure 5: Description of the processing steps executed in real-time inside the underwater vehicle.

Figure 6: Description of the processing steps executed on the on-board system for offline dense 3D reconstruction.

2.3 Semi-global visual odometry

In this approach (see Figure 7), we benefit from the fact that the survey is performed in a structured manner, parallel-track or square-spiral scanning. In both cases, the new images are more likely to be captured at the boundaries of the already scanned part of the area. Moreover, a map of coverage is updated at each step. Based on this map, for new stereo frames at time t , relative pose is estimated thanks to a selection of frames within a certain distance, assumed to be the closest neighboring observations for the pose being currently estimated. The selection of the set of local frames deals with a statistical estimation of neighboring overlapping frames based on the Bhattacharyya distance which is a probabilistic measure of the amount of overlap between two statistical observations, more likely to take account of the pose uncertainty modeled by a full covariance matrix (see Figure 8).

Because of the particular structure of the survey, the selection of frames is composed of two subsets. One local subset involves the current frame with a number of previous frames. And a second subset deals with older frames involved in already optimized poses and trajectory.

For the current pose, bundle adjustment is then performed on both subsets. However, although the parameters from the second subset are included in the optimization, they are masked as static and not optimized, in contrast to the first subset containing the previous frames.

This strategy reduces the complexity of the problem, while having the advantage, like in global approaches, to correct the drifts in odometry estimations thanks to loop closures and overlaps between current and previous trajectories.

Figure 7: Illustration of the strategy of semi-global visual odometry computed to optimize a current camera pose (black pyramid) using already optimized structure of the trajectory in order to preserve global consistency.

Figure 8: Illustration of the estimated relative poses C_i with uncertainty modeled by a full covariance matrix (left) or by a simple Gaussian distribution in all 3D directions (right). On the left scheme, the distance d_2 is statistically estimated to be smaller than d_1 . It is the inverse on the right scheme.

Figure 9: Images of the ROV and the target recorded during the survey. The high concentration of suspended particles during these sea trials can be observed.

3 Results of Seafloor 3D Reconstruction

The survey took place on March 2017, on an underwater site located near the coast of Marseilles. The target, a fiberglass and resin truncated cone shape painted black, has been laid at a depth of 54 m below sea level on a flat muddy seafloor. The survey has consisted of executing along-track crossed rails with the ROV in order to cover a 12×12 meters area. The visibility condition was not completely optimal due to a high concentration of suspended particles. During the image acquisition, the altitude of the ROV from the seabed has been measured on its altimeter between 1.5 and 2 meters.

The total number of acquired images is approximately 3300. The final model contains approximately 38 million 3D points (see Figure 10). The overall 3D model is scaled with an average of 4 millimeters by introducing a stereo base of 0.297 m (value obtained after the triplet calibration, done before the mission in shallow water).

Figure 10: Different view angles of the final 3D model of the target laid on a flat muddy seafloor of 12×12 meters.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

The work presented here, due to a strong collaboration between a research laboratory and a private company specialized in underwater investigation, is an integral part of the French Ministry of Defense’s investigations to use unmanned systems in mine hunting operations.

The proposed bundle adjustment approach performed only on neighboring observations to the current frame largely improves the computation time and leads to constant processing time in long autonomy. It is adapted to the case when the camera moves in a structured manner so that there are overlaps between current trajectory and previously visited areas.

The proposed method is also a step forward compared to local optimization methods because of using a more efficient statistical distance which takes into account the uncertainty of relative pose estimation.

Although, few improvements are planned as future works:

- The whole system will be studied in order to make it more compact and to integrate it on a smaller vehicle more manoeuvrable.
- An inertial sensor will be integrated into the system to take over the visual odometry in the event of losses of optical signal (vehicle too distant from the subject).
- The computing power embedded on the ROV will be increased in order to improve real-time calculation of visual odometry.
- The integration of the visual odometry functionality into an autonomous vehicle with decision making framework in order to achieve autonomous reacquisition and identification missions.
- Further work needs also to be done to reduce the final 3D model’s reconstruction time.

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